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PRODUCTIVENESS OF GAMES IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article under discussion depicts the importance of using games in teaching learners foreign languages and suggests different interesting techniques to improve speaking skills and enhance motivation of the learners. It is considered that using game activities in the lessons not only aid to improve the students' Vocabulary and knowledge of English, but also it makes lessons much more effective, interesting and fruitful.

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Language a foreign learning isn't an easy thing, at the present time it is especially important to know foreign languages. Some people learn languages because they need them for their work, others travel abroad, for the third studying a foreign language is a hobby. Making learning fun motivates students and helps them pay attention and stay focus on the subject. One reason to promote educational games is to encourage students to learn outside of class. We should never forget to consider the duration of the game, if developed in the group or not, the role of teachers and individuals that the game provides, possible difficulties that may occur, competitive or cooperative character of the game etc. For all the foregoing reasons game used different techniques.

These kinds of techniques can classify as:

1. Structural games, which means the ability to control the structure and words

of foreign language.

2. Content games, which means the ability to use foreign language to understand.

3. Communication games, which means the ability to serve foreign language for communicative purposes. When to Use the Games are mostly used when there is some time left at the end of the lesson to keep students quiet. However, Lee (1979, p. 3) proposes that “games should not be regarded as a marginal activity, filling in odd moments when the teacher and class have nothing better to do.” With this in mind, games should be put into the center of classroom teaching and they should not be treated as a merely warm-up activity. Rinvoluceri (1990) clarifies that a game can be used in any of these three stages while using them as a part of grammar instruction:

a) before presenting a given structure, especially to find out diagnostically how much knowledge is already known by the learners;

b) after a grammar presentation to see how much the group have grasped;

c) as a revision of a grammar area. Teachers should be well aware of their roles while using games in their classes. Since it is rather difficult to find a game that meets all the needs of the learners, careful preparation of the teacher is necessary. McCallum (1980, pp. x-xi) suggests that the teacher should organize the game before the instruction. The teacher may need some extra equipment or materials to play the game and most of the time these equipment and materials are not available in the classroom. Before explaining the rules to the class, the teacher should first understand how the game is played. Especially when working with children, the teacher should always be prepared to adapt the game to the givens of the class. After choosing the game, the teacher should explain its rules to the learners in a direct and non-complicated way. Especially for young learners, it may be necessary to use the mother tongue because if these learners cannot understand how to play the game, there is no educational purpose in playing it. Therefore, demonstrations may be beneficial because they can help young learners understand the rules clearly and easily. Moreover, the teacher is not recommended to interrupt a game to correct the mistakes of young learners. According to Celce-Murcia, “interruptions should be as infrequent as possible so as not to detract from the student’s interest in the game. An alternative to immediate correction is to make note of errors and discuss them when the game is over”. In other words, as sudden interruptions may distract learners’ attention, it is better to wait until the game is over to discuss and correct the mistakes of the learners. In addition, appropriate class organization increases the success of a game. Many games require the class to be divided into groups or pairs. This gives the teacher a chance to monitor the activity of the learners while they are playing the game.

McCallum asserts that learners should be in the same team during the year because it both saves the teacher’s time and helps learners develop team spirit that promotes exchange of ideas among themselves. Pair work is also beneficial as it develops learners communication skills. In short, dividing class into pairs and groups enables learners to improve their language and communication skills while promoting competition among the teams or pairs.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹

A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.²

The article considers the role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, sustainable development of tourism occurs as a result of economic integration and the systematic improvement of international relations. With the innovative development of the economy, the role and prestige of tourism in the national economy is growing. Tourism is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy.³

Today richness of Uzbek terminology is mainly due to the use of other languages and word formation is giving. The main factor that determines the stability of a particular terminological system in a particular field is its regularity.⁴

The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural, educational and compensatory competencies.⁵

The main purpose of teaching computer graphics in school in the article is to teach students the order and rules of computer-aided drawing of graphic information, such as drawings, diagrams and schemes, performed in the disciplines of drawing and engineering graphics.⁶

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham’s short story “The Book Bag”. It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁷

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.⁸

Synonyms are formed from the combination of the Greek words *syn* "together" + *onoma* "name", which is an important means of increasing the effectiveness of speech, a clearer, more vivid, logical and diverse expression of thought.⁹

¹ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

² Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

³ Abdullaeva, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).

⁴ Bakhtiyorova, N. M., & Zoirova, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.

⁵ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁶ Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.

⁷ Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM “THE BOOK BAG”. *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОС*.

⁸ Temirova, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE’S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.¹⁰

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.¹¹

In the national economy, as in the economic systems of a number of foreign countries, the concept of public-private partnership (PPP) is being actively implemented.¹²

This article discusses the socio-philosophical importance of gender equality in today's increasingly globalized world. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly in all directions, the current issues of women's legal freedoms, protection of their legitimate interests, social relations of women in society and the development of society, social cohesion, family, traditions, It has been scientifically stated that culture, international and inter-civilizational relations, religion, labor and organization of public organizations are of great importance.¹³

As such, the teacher may find more time to focus on students' language development. Games increase learners' proficiency in practicing grammar communicatively. With the help of grammar games, students can develop their ability in using language as they are given a chance to use language in the situations which have a purpose. Celce-Murcia and Hilles. Therefore, games provide learners with a chance to practice grammar communicatively provided that games attract learners attention to some specific forms before the communicative practice. When this is achieved, the relation between form and discourse is enhanced with the help of games because the form(s) aimed for attention exist naturally in the larger discursive context provided by games. In short, games provide learners with an opportunity to drill and practice grammatical rules and forms by presenting them in a communicative way. In sum, with the introduction of communicative competence, games, which were treated as time fillers or for relaxation activities, began to appear as an indispensable part of any English foreign language teaching programme. Having reviewed the importance and features of games from various angles, the primary aim of this study was to the opinions of EFL teachers on the use of games in their English language classrooms. For this aim, the following research questions were addressed in the study:

- 1) What are EFL teachers' beliefs about the pedagogical value of using games in foreign language classrooms?
- 2) What are the teachers' attitudes towards using games in grammar teaching?

⁹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.

¹⁰ Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.

¹¹ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

¹² Madumarov Talatbek Tolibjonovich, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC - PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7MXR3>

¹³ Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

3) What do teachers think about the effectiveness of using games in teaching grammar to young learners?

4) To what extent do the teachers of EFL make use of games while teaching grammar?

So the games can involve and adapt elements of grammar, lexical, spelling, phonological. etc. Games increase learners achievement and can involve all the basic language skills, i.e., listening, speaking, reading and writing , and a number of skills are often contained in the same game. Games can motivate learners, promote theirs interaction and improve learners' acquisition.

Games also help develop students' communicative competence. Most of the students agreed that new techniques via games had fruitful benefits in improving vocabulary. Effort is required at every moment and must be maintained over a long period of time. As we need meaningfulness in language learning, and authentic use of the language it is useful to follow and create many different techniques and procedures. That through creative procedure we can have an interactive environment which may lead to an improvement in learning a foreign language. According to students' achievements we can asses through utilizing pre and post tests if our students have improved or not, and if our procedure is useful, effective or not. Games and especially educational games are one of the techniques and procedures that the teacher may use in teaching a foreign language. Games are often used as short warm-up activities or when there is some time left at the end of a lesson.

A game should not be regarded as a marginal activity filling in odd moments when the teacher and class have nothing better to do. Games ought to be at the heart of teaching foreign languages, games should be used at all the stages of the lesson, provided that they are suitable and carefully chosen. Games also lend themselves well to revision exercises helping learners recall material in a pleasant, entertaining way. All agree that even if games resulted only in noise and entertained students, they are still worth paying attention to and implementing in the classroom, since they motivate learners, promote communicative competence and generate fluency and may have a significant role in improving a second language acquisition.

One useful strategy to encourage learning a foreign language is using language games. When using games in the classroom, it is beneficial for teachers to have a complete understanding of the definitions of games, which usually are defined as a form of play concerning rules, competition, and an element of fun. Teachers should also consider the advantages of games: the ability to capture students' attention; lower students' stress; and give students the chance for real communication. Lastly teachers need to assess how to use games appropriately in the classroom.

It is important to choose an appropriate time and integrate them into the regular syllabus and curriculum. However, because of the limitations of the syllabus, games often cannot be used, as much as they should be. Therefore, it may be challenging for teachers to try to add some games in class in order to develop students' English proficiency of the target language. Some teachers think that language games are a waste of time and prefer not to use them in classroom since games sometimes have been considered only for its one element that is fun. In fact, games can provide English as a foreign language (EFL) and English as a second language (ESL) students more than that. Among several strategies used to improve students' proficiency such as visual aids, CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning), drama, role-play, and so on, games are another useful strategy to promote students' language proficiency (Richard - Amato, 1996).

This paper aims to give a clear understanding of what games are and why and how games are used in the classroom. Language learning is a hard task which can sometimes be frustrating. Constant effort is required to understand, produce and manipulate the target Language. Well-Chosen games are invaluable as they give students a break and at the same time allow students to practice language skills. Games are highly motivating since they are amusing and at the same time challenging.

Furthermore, they employ meaningful and useful language in real contexts. They also encourage and increase cooperation. "Games are highly motivating because they are amusing and interesting. They can be used to give practice in all language skills and be used to practice many types of communication." (Ersoz, 2000)

According to Richard-Amato (1996), even though games are often associated with fun, we should not lose sight of their pedagogical values, particularly in second language teaching.

Games are effective because they provide motivation, lower students' stress, and give them the opportunity for real communication. The main reason why games are considered effective learning aids is that "they super motivation and students get very absorbed in the competitive aspects of the games; moreover, they try harder at games than in other courses" (Avedon, 1971). Naturally when playing games, students are trying to win or to beat other teams for themselves or on the behalf of their team. They are so competitive while playing because they want to have a turn to play, to score points and to win. In the class, students will definitely participate in the activities. Therefore, it is possible for a teacher to introduce students to new ideas, grammar, and knowledge and so on. As in the dictation game, students are so competitive that they want to finish first and win. It can be clearly seen that games can capture students' attention and participation. They can motivate students to want to learn more. Moreover, they can transform a boring class into a challenging one. Another reason why games are often used in language classes is that they lower students stress in the classroom. In conventional classrooms, there is a lot of stress put on students trying to master the target language. Schultz (1988) said that "...Stress is a major hindrance in language learning process. This process [Learning language in traditional way] is by its nature time consuming and stress provoking raise the stress level to a point at which it interferes with student attention and efficiency and undermines motivation. One method has been developed to make students forget that they are in class relax students by engaging them in stress-reducing task (games)."

There is a high level of stress in the classroom because students have to face unfamiliar or unknown grammatical structures, words, texts and so forth. Therefore, students often feel uncomfortable and insecure in class, which inevitably affects their ability to learn. As a result, games can help lower their anxiety, make them feel comfortable, and want to learn more. It is believed that when students play games, they relax and have fun. Since students know that they are playing games and want to communicate efficiently they do not worry about making mistakes and do not try to correct themselves in every single sentence. When students are free from worry and stress, they can improve their fluency and natural speaking styles.

Next, students learn without realizing that they are learning (Schultz, 1988.) For instance, when playing a game called "What Would You Do If?" students will have to pick one hypothetical question from those that they have written in a box. They might get a question like "What would you do if a lion came into this classroom?" Next they have to pick one answer that they have written before. The answer they get may be "I would be a fly." Usually the question and the answer they get

do not match each other, so students have to use their own imaginations to explain their bizarre answer, and everyone has fun listening to it. The explanation might be "If a lion came into this classroom, I would be a fly because I am a good person, so an angel would come and rescue me by turning me into a fly." While trying to explain, students do not worry too much about grammar mistakes because they want to communicate and to explain why it can happen. Apart from having fun, students do not worry about errors and punishment; moreover, they will learn a grammatical rule and have a chance to use it. Thus, they learn unconsciously-learn without realizing they are learning. Students stop thinking about language and begin using it in a spontaneous and natural manner within the classroom (Schutz, 1988.)

Thinking of the game as a part of a bigger educational process is really in the core mindset that this project wants to promote. Games can do many things very well, but they certainly can not do everything at once.

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